

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: WADADA****FIRST NAME: DANIEL****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA 401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. KABIRU GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

FUNDAMENTALS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

A journey of a thousand miles begins with a single step, so goes the ancient Chinese adage. The ACA-401 course pack period one provides foundational instruction for effective and scholarly academic writing. Visual and written learning materials are comprehensively used to introduce students to academic writing. Being a keen reader, I found the course pack to be my ideal material to grasp the concepts. Taking personal notes in a book as I read, I was able to note down and grasp the key elements which I then later referred to when writing my first Response Paper.

I have thus been oriented on the structure of the EUCILD program that I am pursuing; in particular the structure of the 7 study periods, the expected duration and the fundamentals of academic writing. I studied academic writing as part of my Bachelor's and first Master's Degrees. However, this was a long time ago. Therefore, the ACA 401 period 1 has been very useful in refreshing my mind on the structure of academic papers. I have also been introduced to aspects of academic writing such as the use of Zotero software which I had not used before and Turabian style citation.

By writing my first Response Paper, I am excited to embark on the first step of the long journey of a thousand miles which will culminate in the award of a Master's Degree in Diplomacy and International Affairs. I am indeed proud and happy to have made the choice to pursue this program with EUCLID.

2) FLEXIBILITY

As a full-time employee, working Monday to Friday and sometimes even over weekends with little time to spare. For this reason, I found the structure of the EUCLID program very flexible. It will, therefore, be my goal to make full use of this flexibility by completing a minimum of one study period each week. Where time allows, it is my attention to use any given weekend to complete all seven periods.

3) FUNDAMENTALS OF ESSAY WRITING

The course pack ably illustrated the structure and format of writing good essays which is basically understanding the question, developing my a point of view/argument/thesis point of opinion with which to respond to the question, conducting research, writing the argument starting with a good introduction which introduces my argument then going into the body which contains paragraphs with critical arguments and finally making a critical conclusion which sums up what I gave been arguing about/putting across (EUCLID 2015, 3).

I have written several essays and taken minutes of meetings for several years. However, reading the course pack provided new insight into how to write in a persuasive way that can sway a reader to my point of view. I understood that besides the introduction and conclusion which are very important, the paragraphs in a good essay must contain a sentence which introduces the idea followed by sentences that explain the idea being talked about, followed by evidence to support the point; the evidence may be from the course pack, book, journal or online publication. This evidence is very important because it illustrates that the point being made is backed up by scholarly evidence. Finally, a good essay paragraph must be concluded by analysing the facts contained in the introductory sentences and evidence presented to arrive at a personal scholarly interpretation of the facts that illustrate creative independent thinking (EUCLID 2015, 3).

4) GOOD GRAMMAR

Because academic writers aim to persuade, the grammar used must be of a high standard. EUCLID students are required to choose between using UK or U.S English and to stick to the choice made. Correct punctuation must be used. My academic and working experience of several years will give me a comparative advantage as I have already undertaken three degrees taught using UK English and am also required to write minutes of at least 10 pages every week. Furthermore, the use of software such as Grammarly which I have been introduced to will be a great aid in writing and editing my essays.

5) AVOIDANCE OF PLAGIARISM

The course pack ably articulates that using an author's work without giving credit tantamount to academic theft which is a serious offence, the exception being for instances

where the information used is common knowledge. As a result, am compelled to always cite academic sources using in-text citation or footnotes and where I have used the exact words of the author to use quotation marks. In the same vein, scholars are also reminded not to quote PLAGIARISM lest it will appear that the work belongs to someone else.

In my past experience, while pursuing a different academic program, plagiarism was taken so seriously that before turning in coursework, students were required to upload it to a website which could analyse the material, cross-reference it through all available online resources then provide a report on the originality of the uploaded content. This requirement was a significant deterrent to engaging in plagiarism. Whereas EUCLID does not have a similar requirement, it is my intention to use my previous experience to engage in a high degree of academic honesty by avoiding plagiarism.

7) BE ACTIVE AND CURIOUS!

I connected with the fact that many reading materials will be provided and the onus will be with the student to read as many of them as possible (EUCLID 2015, 2). As an avid reader with an inquisitive mind, I intend to use the vast array of reading materials provided coupled with those derived from personal sources to write well-researched papers. The curiosity of looking beyond the provided reading materials will open up a wealth of additional information with which to successfully undertake the program.

It is also my intention to make use of the hands-on knowledge acquired through my several years of working experience when writing papers to craft critical independent arguments.

6) CONCLUSION

As I start on yet another academic journey after several years of being out of the academic world, the ACA 401 period 1-course pack and videos have greatly refreshed my understanding of academic writing and also introduced me to the structure of EUCLID courses. Emphasis is placed on correctly interpreting a question, developing an argument then writing down that argument based on research and critical thinking. In writing, I am reminded to be persuasive, apply correct grammar and citations. I am also cognizant that zoster software will be a key resource in the successful completion of my program. Whereas I had not used it before, it is my sincere intention to master it with consistent practice to be able to write excellent essays.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1>

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D
Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.